

A study on the effectiveness of hexamethyltriethylenetetraamine ligand in the copper mediated atom transfer radical polymerization of acrylamide

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Atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) of acrylamide was carried out in a glycerol-water (1 : 1 v/v) medium with 2-halopropionamide initiators, CuX (X = Cl, Br)/*N,N,N',N',N'',N''*-hexamethyltriethylenetetraamine (HMTETA) catalyst, CuX₂/HMTETA (20 mol% of CuX/HMTETA) and excess alkali halide (ca. 0.2–1 M) additives. The first-order kinetic plots for the disappearance of monomer were linear when either LiCl (0.2 or 1 M) (or both LiCl (1 M) and CuCl₂/HMTETA (20 mol% of CuCl/HMTETA) were added into the system, to start with. However, in all the cases molecular weights do not increase with conversion. This signifies the uncontrolled nature of polymerization. These results suggest that CuX₂/HMTETA is a poor deactivator as far as the ATRP of acrylamide is concerned.

Atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP)^{1,2} has emerged as a versatile methodology among the various living radical polymerization methods such as (i) nitroxide mediated^{3,4}, (ii) reversible addition fragmentation chain transfer^{5,6} and (iii) degenerative chain transfer^{7,8}. Functional monomers such as (meth)acrylamides, (meth)acrylates, styrenics, acrylonitrile etc. can be polymerized in a controlled manner by using this technique^{1,2}. ATRP relies on rapid reversible deactivation of growing radicals by a transition metal complex at its higher oxidation state which helps to maintain a low steady state concentration of polymer radicals, thereby rendering unimportant the rate of dead polymer formation by way of termination of polymer radicals.

Acrylamide and its derivatives present problems for ATRP^{9,10}. However, Teodorescu and Matyjaszewski achieved reasonably good control on the polymerization¹¹. For example, they obtained polymers with low polydispersity in molecular weight and linear increase of molecular weight with conversion using the CuCl/hexamethyltris-(2-aminoethyl)amine (Me₆TREN) catalyst system for the ATRP of *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide (DMA) in toluene at room temperature. The conversion was, of course, limited and a nonlinear $\ln [M]_0/[M]$ vs t plot was obtained (where $[M]$ and $[M]_0$ are the monomer concentrations at time t and 0, respectively)¹¹ which was attributed to catalyst deactivation. Senoo *et al.* used a ruthenium chloride-based initiating system for the ATRP of DMA in toluene at 80°C and obtained living polymers with controlled molecular weight and a molecular weight polydispersity index (PDI) = 1.6¹². Good control of ATRP

of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) at 20°C was reported by Masci *et al.* in aqueous dimethylformamide (DMF, 1 : 1 v/v) using CuCl/Me₆TREN as the catalyst¹³. On the other hand, the polymerization was uncontrolled with broad PDI (PDI = 2.06) and higher molecular weight than the theoretical value when CuCl/Me₆TREN was replaced by the CuCl/HMTETA catalyst system¹³. The uncontrolled nature of the ATRP of NIPAM in aqueous DMF suggests that the CuCl₂/HMTETA is not a good deactivator as far as the ATRP of acrylamide type of monomer is concerned. Contrary to this latter work Kizhakkedathu *et al.* reported controlled growth of PDMA and PNIPAM brushes with narrow molecular weight distribution for ATRP of the respective monomers from charged surfaces^{14,15} in water using CuCl/HMTETA catalyst at room temperature.

As regards the ATRP of acrylamide itself Writh and Huang¹⁶ prepared polyacrylamide (PAM) with a PDI = 1.11 by carrying out the ATRP in DMF at 130°C using benzyl chloride initiator and CuCl/bipyridine catalyst. Xia and Writh reported surface confined ATRP of acrylamide at room temperature in DMF using CuCl/Me₆TREN catalyst¹⁷. In our previous work¹⁸ we reported that we could not reproduce the results reported by Writh and Huang. However, we succeeded in developing the ATRP of acrylamide in aqueous based media^{18,19}. We explained that in aqueous medium the ATRP is unsuccessful due to a lower rate of deactivation of growing radicals engendered by the aquation or hydrolysis of the transition metal halide complex (deactivator)^{18–20}. The problem was solved using the CuX/bipyridine (bpy) and CuX/pentamethyl-

diethylenetriamine (PMDETA) complex catalyst systems at 130°C with extraneous addition of both CuX_2 (20 mol% of CuX) and an alkali halide e.g. LiX (1 M) ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$)^{18,19}. The addition of the extra deactivator CuX_2/bpy or $\text{CuX}_2/\text{PMDETA}$ into the polymerization medium was necessary in order to increase the deactivation rate. Also, soluble halide salts were required to be added in order to lessen the aquation or hydrolysis of the Cu^{II} halide complexes which are the deactivator. The ligands were selected by means of a screening experiment which measures the molecular weights of PAM samples which form when acrylamide is polymerized in water at 90°C using the water soluble 4,4'-azobis-4-cyanopentanoic acid as the initiator and various cupric chloride complexes with chelating ligands (L) as deactivators¹⁸. The molecular weights as discerned from gpc traces decrease with the increase in the ability of deactivation by the CuCl_2/L complexes. Accordingly, the following order of ligands with increased deactivation capability of the Cu^{II} complex was arrived at: Me_4 cyclam < TMEDA < HMTETA < PMDETA < bpy (Me_4 cyclam = 1,4,8,11-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane, TMEDA = tetramethylethylenediamine). However, PMDETA worked better than bpy in the ATRP of acrylamide which was attributed to a slightly alkaline pH that was required to be used in the bpy based system in contrast to the neutral (pH = 7) pH used when PMDETA was the ligand¹⁹. At the alkaline pH the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{bpy}$ complex undergoes more hydrolysis as well as dimerization²¹ which reactions make it a less powerful deactivator. HMTETA was the 3rd best deactivator according to our screening experiment.

In this work we have examined the efficacy of HMTETA for the ATRP of acrylamide. As stated in a preceding paragraph of this section Kizhakkedathu *et al.* reportedly succeeded in using the HMTETA ligand for the Cu mediated ATRP of DMA and NIPAM in water^{14,15}. It is therefore of interest to examine if HMTETA can be used as the ligand for carrying out the ATRP of acrylamide as well in a water based medium.

Experimental

Materials : Acrylamide (99+ % electrophoresis-grade; Sigma), glycerol (G.R. 99%, E. Merck), HMTETA (98%), bipyridine (bpy 99+ %), 2-chloropropionamide (2-Cl-PA) and 2-bromopropionamide (2-Br-PA) (all Aldrich products), were used as received. CuBr (98%, Aldrich) and CuCl (98%, B.D.H.) were purified by washing with the corresponding acids (10% HX in water) followed by methanol and diethyl ether in a Schlenk tube

under nitrogen atmosphere. Commercial distilled water was redistilled over alkaline permanganate.

Polymerization method :

An example of polymerization with the 2-Cl-PA/ CuCl /HMTETA initiator/catalyst system is as follows. In a 8 cm × 2.5 cm test tube provided with B-19 standard joint was taken 3 ml of a mixture of glycerol and water (1 : 1 v/v) which was then purged with nitrogen for 15 min. LiCl (132 mg, 3.18 mmol), acrylamide (AA) (900 mg, 12.67 mmol), CuCl (5.94 mg, 0.06 mmol) and HMTETA (20.8 mg, 0.12 mmol) were added sequentially in that order at room temperature under nitrogen. The pH was adjusted to 7 using dilute HCl or HBr. Working at a higher pH *ca.* 8.5 yields polymer with broader molecular weight distribution (MWD). After a further 15 min of nitrogen purge, 2-Cl-PA (6.5 mg, 0.06 mmol) was added to the admixture. The reaction vessel was sealed by a rubber septum which was secured by Cu wire and placed in an oil bath maintained at a temperature of 130°C. After a 22 h reaction time the reaction vessel was taken out of the bath and the polymer was precipitated into methanol. The precipitated polymer was separated by centrifugation, redissolved in a minimum amount of water and reprecipitated into methanol. This step was done to free the polymer from any entrapped glycerol. The polymer was dried in a vacuum oven at 45°C for 48 h. Conversion was 65%. The \bar{M}_n and PDI of the polymer were 10800 and 1.65 respectively. For kinetic experiments samples were withdrawn from time to time using gas tight syringes.

Characterization :

Molecular weight and polydispersity :

The \bar{M}_n and MWD were determined by gpc at room temperature (*ca.* 30°C) using a Waters Model 510 HPLC Pump, Waters series 400 differential refractometer and three Waters Ultrahydrogel columns of 500, 250 and 120 Å pore size and 10, 6, and 6 μm bead size respectively which were preceded by an ultrahydrogel guard column. An aqueous solution of 0.1 M NaNO_3 was used as eluant at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. Before injection into the gpc system the polymer solutions were treated with the cation-exchange resin Dowex® 50W (Fluka) to free them from Cu salts. They were then filtered through a prefilter-filter combination system compatible with aqueous solutions. Polyethylene glycol as well as polyethylene oxide, obtained from Waters, was used as calibration standards. However, since the hydrodynamic volumes of the standards are not likely to be the same as those of PAM of

same molecular weights, the gpc traces were used only to calculate the PDI. The actual molecular weights were measured by the viscometric method for which the intrinsic viscosity was determined by the single point method using eq. (1)²²,

$$[\eta] = \frac{\sqrt{2\eta_{sp} - 2 \ln \eta_{rel}}}{c} \quad (1)$$

The viscosity was determined using aqueous 0.5 M NaCl as the solvent at 25°C. The weight average molecular weight (\bar{M}_w) was calculated using the following Mark-Houwink relation²³,

$$[\eta] = 7.19 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_w^{0.77} \quad (2)$$

The constants in the above equation were determined by Klein and Conrad using unfractionated polyacrylamide samples whose molecular weights were determined by light scattering method²³. The number average molecular weight \bar{M}_n was calculated from \bar{M}_w using the PDI values of the samples determined from the gpc traces.

Results and discussion

Table 1 gives the results of ATRP of acrylamide in glycerol-water (1 : 1 v/v) medium at 130°C using 2-Cl-PA initiator and CuCl/HMTETA catalyst with or without the use of additives. Kinetic plots for the disappearance of monomer ($\ln [M]_0/[M]$ vs t plots where $[M]_0$ and $[M]$ are the concentration of monomer at time, $t = 0$ and t respectively) are shown in Fig. 1. The plots are nonlinear for the systems when no additive or only CuCl₂/HMTETA (20 mol% of CuCl/HMTETA) were added (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 2 respectively). But addition of either LiCl (0.2 or 1 M) (lines 3 and 4) or both LiCl (1 M) and CuCl₂/HMTETA (20 mol% of CuCl/HMTETA) (line 5) resulted in linear plots. The nonlinear $\ln [M]_0/[M]$ vs t plots in the absence of LiCl (curves 1 and 2) suggest the occurrence of bimolecular termination reaction to a significant extent. The linear plots obtained in the presence of LiCl (0.2 or 1 M) or in the presence of both CuCl₂/HMTETA and LiCl suggest that for such systems the radical concentrations are nearly constant throughout the reaction period which is one of the requirements of a living radical polymerization.

The molecular weights of the polymers do not increase with conversion even in the experiments which yield linear kinetic plots (sets 3 to 5, Table 1). In fact, M_n decreases with conversion. However, the PDI values for these systems are almost as good as the best systems worked out earlier^{18,19} using either bpy or PMDETA

Table 1. Results of ATRP of acrylamide at 130°C using 2-chloropropionamide as the initiator in glycerol-water medium (1 : 1 v/v). [Acrylamide] = 4.22 M, [2-Cl-PA] = [CuCl] = 0.008 M, [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [HMTETA] = 1 : 2

Set	In presence of		Time (h)	% Conversion	M_n^a	M_n^b (theo)	PDI
	LiCl (M)	CuCl ₂ :CuCl					
1 ^c	0	0	0.5	40	23400	15000	2
			1.5	46	-	-	-
			3	48	-	-	-
			5.5	50	20000	18700	1.8
2 ^c	0	0.2	0.666	15	21000	5600	1.82
			1.16	24	-	-	-
			3	38	-	-	-
			5	42	19600	15700	1.74
3 ^c	0.2	0	0.17	15	54500	5600	1.53
			0.42	27	52800	10100	1.52
			0.84	50	40600	18700	1.5
			1.42	67	38300	25100	1.48
4	1	0	0.16	17	72800	6375	1.36
			0.33	27	68000	10100	1.37
			0.64	50	56600	18700	1.5
			0.84	62	52100	23200	1.49
5	1	0.2	1	26	41300	9700	1.66
			3	72	40200	27000	1.65
			6.5	90	39500	33700	1.67
			8.5	96	38000	36000	1.66

^afrom \bar{M}_w determined by viscometry and using gpc determined PDI (see experimental).

^b \bar{M}_n (theory) = Amount (g) of monomer polymerized/mole of initiator used.

^c[CuCl] : [HMTETA] = 1 : 1 (mole ratio).

ligands. Remarkably, in the system where LiCl (1 M) was used as the additive the PDI was unexpectedly lower (1.36–1.37) in the lower conversion region (17–27%) (vide set 4, Table 1). However, M_n is much greater than the theoretical molecular weight. The much greater values of M_n than the theory and the decrease of M_n with conversion suggest that the CuCl/HMTETA based catalyst system gives poor control on polymerization. It behaves more like a conventional free radical polymerization.

Fukuda *et al.* derived rate equations for ATRP systems for different situations²⁴.

When the inequality (3) given below applies

$$2 t R_i^{3/2} (k_t K^2 [A]^2 [P-X]_0^2)^{1/2} \gg 1 \quad (3)$$

(where R_i , k_t , K , A , $P-X$ and t respectively are the rate of initiation, rate constant for termination, the ATRP equi-

Fig. 1. $\ln [M]_0/[M]$ vs t plots for the ATRP of acrylamide using 2-chloropropionamide (2-Cl-PA) initiator and CuCl/HMTETA catalyst at 130°C in glycerol-water (1 : 1 v/v) medium with or without additives. [Acrylamide] = 4.22 M, [2-Cl-PA] = [CuCl] = 0.008 M; $[Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [HMTETA] = 1 : 2$. Curves : (1) no additive, (2) in presence of 0.0016 M CuCl₂/HMTETA, (3) in presence of 0.2 M LiCl, (4) in presence of 1 M LiCl, (5) in presence of 0.0016 M CuCl₂/HMTETA and 1 M LiCl.

librium constant, the deactivator, the polymer concentration (molar) and time), the kinetic equation for monomer disappearance was deduced to be

$$\ln ([M]_0/[M]) = k_p (R_i/k_t)^{1/2} t \quad (4)$$

where k_p is the rate constant of propagation. Eq. (4) is the same as that for a conventional free radical polymerization with a stationary state. It is devoid of deactivator concentration and the rate of deactivation.

The uncontrolled molecular weight suggests a slow rate of deactivation of polyacrylamide radicals by the deactivator CuCl₂/HMTETA. The situation did not improve even when LiCl (1 M) was added into the polymerization system, to start with, to prevent aquation/hydrolysis of the cupric complexes. This result suggests that the poor control is not due to the aquation or hydrolysis of the deactivator but due to the intrinsically lower deactivation rate effected by CuCl₂/HMTETA. This conclusion is substantiated by the results of the ligand screening experiment discussed in our earlier work¹⁸ and stated in the introduction of this paper.

ATRP was also conducted in glycerol-water medium at 130°C using CuBr/HMTETA catalyst and 2-Br-PA initiator with or without the extraneous addition of CuBr₂

and KBr. In these systems also polymers with molecular weights much greater than the theoretical values are produced. Moreover, the M_n s do not increase with conversion as is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Evolution of M_n and PDI with conversion in the ATRP of acrylamide at 130°C in glycerol-water (1 : 1 v/v) medium using 2-propionamide initiator (2-Br-PA). [Acrylamide] = 4.22 M, [2-Br-PA] = [CuBr] = [HMTETA] = 0.008 M, KBr = 1 M. Filled and open symbols represent the molecular weight and PDI respectively. Solid line represents theoretical molecular weight.

It is therefore concluded that, the ATRP of acrylamide is uncontrolled when CuX/HMTETA complex is used as the catalyst system. The uncontrolled nature of polymerization is attributed to the slower deactivation of polyacrylamide radicals by the CuX₂/HMTETA deactivator. The latter result was established earlier by us in a ligand screening experiment¹⁸. The present work is in contrast to the successful ATRP of the acrylamide derivatives, DMA and NIPAM, effected by CuCl/HMTETA catalyst as reported by Kizhakkedathu *et al.*^{14,15}.

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